

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: VEGEPOLYS VALLEY

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"Let's meet!" Event Validation Report – France

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PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY for the organisation and validation of the Celebrate Local Heroes event in Auvergne-Rhone-Alpes, Lyon on 20/01/2023. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Celebrate Local Heroes event in Auvergne-Rhone-Alpes, Lyon.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

- Celebrate local heroes is the event selected by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY. During the SIRHA (International exhibition for catering, hospitality and food) two Local Heroes have been nominated, the 20/01/2023 at 6.00 P.M on Credit Agricole’s stand. Crédit Agricole Centre France is a partner of this prize. It offered its stand for the award ceremony and a financial support to the two winners.
- It was an incredible opportunity to celebrate this event during the SIRHA where a lot of food innovation professionals have been gathered.
- Two prizes have been delivered:
 - The CONCEPT PRIZE: VEGEPOLYS VALLEY rewarded the most innovative SFSC concept (purchase resale in SFSC and local food)
 - The PRODUCT PRIZE: VEGEPOLYS VALLEY rewarded the most innovative processing of local food products (promotion of a local product)

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Introduction	Presentation of the partners, the prizes, the objectives by a representative of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	20/01/2023 6.00 P.M	Credit Agricole stand, in the SIRHA LYON
Conference	“Eat locally, sustainable or not “ by Yuna Chiffolleau (spokesperson of French MAP, expert in economic sociology and director of research at RMT local food)	20/01/2023 6.15 P.M	Credit Agricole stand, in the SIRHA LYON
Awards	Presentation of the two prizes and the two winners by Samuel DUQUET, (spokesperson of Crédit Agricole Centre France)	20/01/2023 6.45 P.M	Credit Agricole stand, in the SIRHA LYON
Pitch of the winners	Brief presentation of the two selected projects (the two winners)	20/01/2023 6.50 P.M	Credit Agricole stand, in the SIRHA LYON

Cocktail	Sharing of a cocktail with everyone present in order to discuss and create partnerships	20/01/2023 7.15 P.M	Credit Agricole stand, in the SIRHA LYON
End of the event	The SIRHA closes at 8.30 PM	20/01/2023 8.30 P.M	Credit Agricole stand, in the SIRHA LYON

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

- The “Celebrate local heroes” took place on the Crédit Agricole stand, in Eurexpo Lyon during the SIRHA’s exhibition.
- There was a central island with spaces and chairs all around, a screen to project information during the event and a microphone and speakers.
- The cocktail has been booked with the only caterer dedicated for the SIRHA.
- Two posters were printed to promote the Agrobridges’ project.
- Two checks illustration were also printed for the award ceremony.

Figure 1: Presentation of the two winners: mPmC and Limoune

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material (website)	In-house	2 person days
Graphic designers	1	Print the posters	External	0.25 person day
Catering	2	Food and drinks for guests	External	N/A
Global organisation	3	Rating scale, application file, promotion, communication	In-house	12 person day
Notation/Jury	3	Rating of the application file received	In-house and External	1 person day
Representation of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	1	Presentation of the event, the objectives	In-house	0.5 person day
Local food and SFSC expert	1	Conference "Eat locally, sustainable or not"?	External	1 person day
Award ceremony	1	Present the winners and award ceremony	External	1 person day

2.4 Event material

The event graphic material used for this event are two posters made by the agroBRIDGES Dissemination Manager and translated by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY. We also had the Informed Consent Form and the Feedback survey with agroBRIDGES logo.

Figure 2: Printed posters for the Celebrate Local Heroes event

Figure 3: Positioning of promo material on the event site

We also created an application form and a scoring grid for all the submissions and rating of candidate files for the local Heroes Awards.

Figure 4: Candidate folders

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Créer des liens producteurs-consommateurs

DOSSIER DE CANDIDATURE AU PRIX DES HEROS
LOCAUX

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

DOSSIER DE CANDIDATURE AU PRIX DES HEROS LOCAUX

Le dépôt final doit être effectué en ligne avant le **15 janvier 2023** via le formulaire ci-dessous.
Nous vous conseillons de préparer vos réponses en amont et de les stocker.

* Champs obligatoires

Coordonnées du contact

Nom * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Prénom * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Âge * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Code postal * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Ville * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Téléphone * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Adresse email * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

SIRET entreprise * : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Votre projet

Sur quelle (s) thématique (s) est-il positionné ? * :

Concept de circuit-court alimentaire local innovant (Prix CONCEPT)

Transformation de produits alimentaires locaux innovante (Prix PRODUIT)

Quels produits sont concernés par l'activité présentée ?

Légumes

Fruits

Produits laitiers

Produits carnés

Plantes aromatiques

Autres : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Décrivez votre produit ou service : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

DOSSIER DE CANDIDATURE AU PRIX DES HEROS LOCAUX

En quoi votre projet est-il innovant ? (2000 il innovant caractères maximum) * :

Savez-vous si d'autres entreprises réalisent la même activité que vous ou s'en rapprochent ? (2000 caractères maximum) * :

Décrivez votre programme d'actions pour l'année 2023 (2000 caractères maximum) * :

Dans quel(s) territoire(s) allez-vous développer vos activités ? * :

Quels sont vos besoins en matière d'accompagnement et de partenariat, notamment par rapport à VEGEPOLYS VALLEY ? :

DOSSIER DE CANDIDATURE AU PRIX DES HEROS LOCAUX

Funded by the
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Suite à l'analyse des candidatures par le jury, le pôle VEGEPOLYS VALLEY annoncera les 2 lauréats sous forme d'actualités sur le site internet et sur les réseaux sociaux. Par anticipation, nous vous remercions de renseigner les 8 points suivants avec de l'information non confidentielle.

- **Date de création de l'entreprise** : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer une date.
- **Fondateur(s)** : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.
- **Nom de l'entreprise** : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.
- **Présentation de l'activité en 2 ou 3 phrases (15 à 30 mots)** : ambition, mission ou objectif : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.
- **Présentation de l'innovation (en 100 mots)** : descriptif et caractère innovant par rapport à l'existant Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.
- **Photo ou visuel du produit ou service en format .jpg**

- Site internet
- Compte(s) sur les réseaux sociaux
- Coordonnées pour être joint par des journalistes : tél. ou mail

En déposant cette fiche résumée, vous accordez à VEGEPOLYS VALLEY le droit de la diffuser, y compris avec les images, dans le cadre de la communication sur le projet ou le prix des Héros Locaux 2022-2023.

DOSSIER DE CANDIDATURE AU PRIX DES HEROS LOCAUX

Si vous n'êtes pas lauréat, nous pouvons toutefois faire figurer cette présentation en tant que candidat sur notre site et nos réseaux sociaux. Cette opportunité vous intéresse-t-elle ? * :

- Oui
- Non

J'autorise les chargés de mission du pôle à prendre connaissance des éléments ci-dessus dans le cadre de l'accord de confidentialité qu'ils ont signé pour leurs activités dans les projets innovants du pôle * :

- Oui
- Si non, précisez : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Comment avez-vous connu le prix des héros locaux ? * :

- Par la presse
- Par le site Internet
- Par un mail
- Par LinkedIn
- Par Twitter
- Par un courrier
- Par une affiche
- Par un flyer
- Via votre réseau

Pièces à joindre impérativement à votre dossier de candidature

- Une copie recto-verso de la pièce d'identité ou du permis de séjour au format .pdf ou .jpeg (max 2 Mo).
- Une copie de votre extrait Kbis datant de moins de 3 mois : Format .jpeg ou .pdf (max. 2 Mo)
- Une copie de votre Relevé d'Identité Bancaire (RIB)

En cas de besoin , contactez-nous à l'adresse suivante : maiti.boussit@vegepolys-valley.eu

DOSSIER DE CANDIDATURE AU PRIX DES HEROS LOCAUX

Si vous n'êtes pas lauréat, nous pouvons toutefois faire figurer cette présentation en tant que candidat sur notre site et nos réseaux sociaux. Cette opportunité vous intéresse-t-elle ? * :

- Oui
- Non

J'autorise les chargés de mission du pôle à prendre connaissance des éléments ci-dessus dans le cadre de l'accord de confidentialité qu'ils ont signé pour leurs activités dans les projets innovants du pôle * :

- Oui
- Si non, précisez : Cliquez ou appuyez ici pour entrer du texte.

Comment avez-vous connu le prix des héros locaux ? * :

- Par la presse
- Par le site Internet
- Par un mail
- Par LinkedIn
- Par Twitter
- Par un courrier
- Par une affiche
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Pièces à joindre impérativement à votre dossier de candidature

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- Une copie de votre Relevé d'Identité Bancaire (RIB)

En cas de besoin , contactez-nous à l'adresse suivante : maiti.boussit@vegepolys-valley.eu

Figure 5: Candidate evaluation form and scoring grid

Critères		Points	Notation	Commentaires
1-Présentation	-Qualité et rédaction du dossier -Qualité de l'argumentaire -Précision, clarté et complétude du dossier	/3		
2-Adéquation aux objectifs du concours	-Entreprise française, déclarée -Travaillant sur une innovation en CC et/ou produits locaux (sains)	/2		
3-Ambition et pertinence de l'innovation	-Pertinence du sujet/solution apportée -Clarté sur le modèle économique de la structure -Projets et vision sur 3-5 ans	/6		
4-Faisabilité et impacts	-Durabilité du projet, -Impact pour la structuration de l'écosystème local -Solution réplicable sur divers territoires -Création d'emplois directs ou indirects -Identification des freins/obstacles - Capacité du projet à générer un effet d'entraînement pour aller vers une initiative plus ambitieuse, pour inspirer d'autres acteurs sur d'autres territoires ?	/8		
Critère BONUS	Projet coup de cœur	/1		
TOTAL /commentaire global				

COMMENTAIRES :

TOTAL : /20

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

At the beginning of the organisation of our “Celebrate Local Heroes”, we wanted the intervention of an expert about SFSC. In our MAP’s members we have the chance to have Yuna Chiffolleau’s participation, expert in SFSC (expert in economic sociology and director of research at RMT local food). Early in the thinking process (July 2022) we talked with her and organized the event with her.

Then, to organize the Prize of Local Heroes, we needed a place and a reward.

First (August 2022), we thought to organize the event in Paris (to involve as many people as possible) but there was no related event that could make people come. That’s why we changed our plans and decided to organize the reward of the prize during an event where the people we focused on are already present.

The SIRHA (International exhibition for catering, hospitality and food) seemed to be the best idea for us: an event in January and in Lyon.

The Credit Agricole centre France bank is a membership of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, involved in several projects with the association. We knew that they were interested to work about projects related to agriculture and SFSC and they had a stand on the SIRHA. We presented them the project and effectively, Crédit Agricole Centre France answered positively.

Referring to the reward, at the beginning we thought about a free membership to VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, a personalised support from VEGEPOLYS VALLEY about communications tips, etc. However, it is not the first prize organized by VEGEPOLYS VALLEY and we know that if we want to have candidates, it is not enough for a national event. People wants to win money... it was one of the rare solutions we found to be sure to get participants and involve the candidates. For this purpose, we contacted again the Crédit Agricole Centre France (which is a bank) to propose them to be even more engaged in the Prize of Local Heroes by rewarding the winners with money.

Then, we started to write the application form validated by Yuna Chiffolleau and we talked about the organization of the event with the Crédit Agricole (creation of bank check illustration, catering), the speeches, interventions and timing of the event.

One week before the event, we stopped the submission of the candidature files. Samuel DUQUET (Crédit Agricole Centre France), Yuna Chiffolleau (RMT local food) and Joséphine LAVIGNE (VEGEPOLYS VALLEY) noted and commented the files to determine the two winners.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

To promote and communicate about the event, we established a big list of contacts:

- Start-ups and SMEs,
- producers,
- chambers of agriculture,
- associations and companies related to FSCS,
- inter-profession from different agricultural sectors
- public institutions
- cooperatives
- regional and local authorities

With this list of contacts representing nearly 200 structures, we sent an e-mail (1.5 month before the event) and two recordings (1 and 2 weeks before the event), about the event. We also made publications on VEGEPOLYS VALLEY social networks and website (16.12.2022). With this communication and promotion about our Let's Meet event we knew that the sharing of the information and the word of mouth will work.

In our mails and posts we highlighted that for all the candidates to the Local Heroes Prize, the entrance to the SIRHA show was offered.

2.7 Applications and candidates' evaluation

To be able to apply, the structures had to be declared and propose an innovative SFCS concept or an innovative transformation of local agri-food products.

The files were marked by the various juries according to the following points:

- The quality of the file (writing, arguments, ...)
- Innovation in short circuit and/or local products
- The ambition and relevance of the innovation (economic model, 3-5-year vision, solution provided)
- The feasibility and impacts of the project 'sustainability, local ecosystem, replicability, job creation, identification of obstacles, ambitions
- A bonus point could be given for "favorite" projects

In total, **15 applications** have been submitted, out of which:

- 7 for the CONCEPT PRIZE
- 8 for the PRODUCT PRIZE

Several exchanges took place between the different juries in order to understand the stakes of the files and try to score uniformly.

Some files sparked debates between the people who rated the files on the solutions provided, the relevance and viability of the projects.

The products and services offered in the application files are varied:

- **SPORABICA:** Substrate based on coffee grounds for use in mushroom houses (non-energy intensive)
- **Approlocal.fr:** Online ordering tool for local products from catering professionals
- **Biotifood:** Valorisation of co-products in the form of lacto fermented sauces, juices and sodas
- **La ferme des Pampilles:** 100% local pork production - breeding, cutting and processing on the farm
- **Laboheme-Codina:** Range of natural and local cosmetics, based on pumpkin seed oil cake
- **Le champs des saveurs:** Complete offer of farm products (food and others) in SFSC - over 200 m², 140 producers supply the store and 85% of them are present within a radius of 50 km around the store.
- **Limoune:** Vegetation of the aperitif based on lacto fermented foods from organic and local vegetables and fair trade spices
- **Lisy:** Creation of communities in short circuits thanks to an order management tool as simple as an email and accessible free of charge

- **Loqualis:** Grouped deliveries of local products to companies, gifts from companies/customers, discovery of the territory through workshops in partnership with the artisans and producers of the territory.
- **mPmC:** Linking actors and tools promoting a short circuit that is local and integrates the 3 pillars of sustainability.
- **Resan:** Modular processing workshops to be installed on farms - enhancing harvests and production, support for farms throughout the processing process, logistical, marketing and sales support, job creation.
- **Santalim:** Preparation of nutritious country cereals, in less than 5 minutes of cooking
- **Solidarifood:** Training in the challenges of food waste for all audiences (schools, professionals and consumers) and implementation of actions (distribution of foodstuffs, the implementation of shared fridges and collaborative cooking workshops).
- **Valiriz'me:** Range of snacks enriched with vegetable proteins based on fruits and/or vegetables from by-products of agri-food industries and unsold supermarkets.
- **Zalg:** Products based on cultured seaweed (seaweed to fry in the form of cubes)

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

- Few minutes before the beginning of the event, we met our partners on the credit agricole stand: Samuel DUQUET from the Crédit Agricole and Yuna CHIFFOLEAU from the RMT. Both winners were also in advance. We put the posters, tested the microphone and organized the place. When ready, we took time to discuss with the people present: candidates and unknown people/structures.
- The day of the event, we had a major strike in France and unfortunately a lot of people, supposed to come to the event, couldn't come because of cancelled trains. That's why, the days before the event, we called the two winners to make sure they were there.
- The intervention of Yuna CHIFFOLEAU about SFSC have been really interested. Event if not a lot of people were present, they seem captivated. Some people who passed by the stand by chance also stopped by to listen to Yuna speech.
- After the reward of the prize, it has been a really good moment in a restricted committee to discuss together about the activities of all participants as well as the problems and obstacles encountered.

Figure 3: Pictures of the event

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers/ candidate structures	9
Consumers	3
Media, journalists	1
Caterer	2
Partners	4
Collaborators	4
Total	23

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question						
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	Yes		No		Not Sure	
	5		0		0	
Did you find this competition-based event informative about producers, initiatives and supply chains in your region bringing local food closer to you?	Very informative	Relatively Informative	Neutral	Not Informative	Not Informative at all	No answer
	2	2	1	0	0	0
Was this event helpful for you to appreciate more the value of your local food and the people working to produce it or bring it to you?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	No answer
	2	1	2	0	0	0
Did you find the work or activity of the winning case valuable for your health, the environment, and the society?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	No answer
	3	0	2	0	0	0
Did you find enough information about how and where to find the people, businesses and initiatives you've met to buy local food?	Enough and very precise information	Enough information but I would need more details	Enough information but I need to search further on my own	Not enough information	No information at all	No answer
	4	0	0	1	0	0
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	No answer
	5	0	0	0	0	0

Testimonial

“A big thank you for this prize, which really touches us and which gave us renewed energy to give our concept of local and SFSC. Innovating is not easy in France and this award will really help us a lot! The format of the presentation of this award also allowed for great encounters which could, perhaps, trigger collaborations. Finally, thank you for offering us membership in VEGEPOLYS VALLEY, looking forward to discovering all the possibilities of working together as well as the resources and supports to help us move forward.”

Jean-François TEDESCO, representative of the mPmC company - Local Heroes award winner

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The organization of that kind of event is really relevant for all the local agri-food ecosystem and organization. Structures, producers were happy to see this event and they applied from all parts of France. We received calls after the event to know if this event will be renewed next year.

Question #2: Would you organize the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Why not. It is quite easy to organize this event. Moreover, every year the event will be more and more famous. The only thing we need is to find somebody to finance the reward. To do the Local Prize in a big event it is a good idea. However, it is not best to do it at the end of the day because people, after a day in an exhibition are tired and don’t want to stay longer.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, it was easy to adapt the templates and guidelines depending on the event.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, perfectly.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, perfectly.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Many factors have affected the success of the event:

- The Local Heroes Prize has been organized a Friday at 6 p.m. For people coming far from the place of the event, they had to travel during their weekend.
- The Local Heroes Prize has been organized after a day of exhibition: people are tired and want to come back home.
- A huge strike in France that day: lot of people had to cancel their trip to Lyon because there were no trains anymore.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Not so much to recommend improving the guidelines: maybe a Gantt chart? Proposing an application form model and a scoring grid can provide a first working basis to find the relevant criteria to ask for according to the event created.

5. Conclusions

Even if not so many people and structures assisted to the Local Heroes' Prize, the few people present appreciated the event, the interventions we organized and the time where everybody could discuss together: promote its activity, extend its network and make new potential partners.

A Local Heroes Prize is quite easy to organize and definitely appreciated by the producers and structures acting for the SFSC. Most of the time, they are not enough valorised and rewarded and often they need help to develop their activities: money, support in communication, strategy, marketing, recruitment, ... That's why, this kind of event is really helpful to them.